

Addendum to “The health and environmental impact of dental amalgam and alternative restorative materials: a systematic review”

This addendum relates to the systematic review titled “The health and environmental impact of dental amalgam and alternative restorative materials: a systematic review”, which was undertaken by the Exeter PRP Evidence Review Facility.¹ The addendum sets out how the identification of a study report by Harding et al. after the systematic review was completed has an impact on how the findings relating to environmental impact should be interpreted.² However, we note at the outset that the overall conclusion of the systematic review remains the same. Specifically, more comparative evidence is required which clearly shows the relative environmental impacts of different restorative materials in real world settings.

Summary of recently identified study report

The study report by Harding et al. was shared with the Exeter PRP Evidence Review Facility during peer review for an academic journal publication (in press).² Harding et al.² is a sibling paper of one of the studies already included in the review: Binner et al.³ Harding et al. reports additional data from this study– specifically, levels of total suspended solids (TSS) in dental wastewater from dental activity involving dental amalgam, resin-based composite (RBC) and glass-ionomer cement (GIC) materials.² The findings show that levels of TSS in wastewater from GIC and RBC restorative materials are higher than those from dental amalgam. Furthermore, levels of TSS from GIC and RBC were higher than permissible limits according to the Protection of the Environment Act (2003) and EU Directive 91/271/EEC. Contrastingly, levels of TSS were within limits for dental amalgam, albeit above permissible limits for total dissolved solids. Importantly, the dental clinics from which wastewater samples were collected in Harding et al. used amalgam separators to reduce the amount of amalgam which is discharged into the wastewater.²

How this changes the interpretation of findings in the systematic review

This finding is important for interpreting the findings of the systematic review because it challenges a key finding which was based on a paper by Majstorovic et al.⁴ Majstorovic et al. compared animal toxicity of dental amalgam, RBC and GIC, and found that dental amalgam was the most harmful, followed by RBC and GIC.⁴ This suggests that dental amalgam is more harmful than RBC or GIC. However, crucially, this study was based in a lab setting, and it is not clear whether amalgam separators were used, or if there was an attempt to simulate the effect of amalgam separators. Contrastingly, in Harding et al. (in which amalgam separators were present) total suspended solids of GIC and RBC were higher than dental amalgam, and were associated with animal toxicity.² Furthermore, TSS relating to dental amalgam were within permissible limits, whereas GIC and RBC were above permissible limits.

Thus, the finding in Harding et al. shows the importance of amalgam separators for reducing toxic discharge from amalgam-based restorative activity, and also suggests that amalgam separators are comparatively less effective at limiting toxic discharge from RBC and GIC restorative activity. This is an important nuance in the interpretation of the findings in the systematic review. However, it is not established that RBC and GIC materials are more toxic than dental amalgam, as Harding et al. only compared levels of TSS for dental amalgam, RBC and GIC, not animal toxicity. It is also important to note that the relative amounts of dental amalgam, RBC and GIC which were used in Harding et al. is not clear, meaning that levels of TSS may be higher simply due to more activity relating to RBC and GIC.^{2,3} As such, the overall conclusion that more comparative evidence is required remains the same.

References

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3. Binner H, Kamali N, Harding M, Sullivan T. Characteristics of wastewater originating from dental practices using predominantly mercury-free dental materials. *Sci Total Environ.* 2022;814:152632.
4. Majstorovic M, Babic Brcic S, Malev O, et al. Environmental implications of dental restorative materials on the zebrafish *Danio rerio*: Are dental chair drainage systems an emerging environmental threat? *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol.* 2024;110:104499.